

TRENDS AND MOTIVES IN MEDICAL TERMINOLOGY TEACHING

TIBBIYOT TERMINOLOGIYASINI O'QITISHDAGI TENDENTSIYALAR VA MOTIVLAR

ТЕНДЕНЦИИ И МОТИВЫ ПРЕПОДАВАНИЯ МЕДИЦИНСКОЙ ТЕРМИНОЛОГИИ

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***Annotation.** This article discusses the trends in teaching medical terminology at medical schools. The activities of the newly established Central Asian Medical University in Fergana City are highlighted. Reflections on the teaching of medical terms, Latin, and important aspects of language learning are then presented.*

***Keywords:** Medical terms, Latin, Central Asian Medical University, Language learning.*

***Annotatsiya.** Ushbu maqolada tibbiyot fakultetlarida tibbiy terminlar o'qitish borasidagi tendensiyalar haqida so'z yuritiladi. Fargonada yangi tashkil etilgan Central Asian Medical University faoliyati urg'ulanadi. So'ngra tibbiy terminlarni o'qitish, lotin tili va til o'rganishga doir muhim jihatlar haqida mulohazalar keltiriladi.*

***Kalit so'zlar:** tibbiyot atamaları, lotin tili, Central Asian Medical University, til o'rganish.*

***Аннотация.** В данной статье рассматриваются тенденции преподавания медицинской терминологии в медицинских вузах. Освещена деятельность вновь созданного Среднеазиатского медицинского университета в городе Фергана. Затем представлены размышления о преподавании медицинских терминов, латыни и важных аспектах изучения языка.*

***Ключевые слова:** Медицинские термины, латынь, Среднеазиатский медицинский университет, изучение языков.*

Introduction. Teaching medical terminology can be a difficult task, but there are several strategies that can prove effective [1]. Firstly, use visual aids: Medical terminology can be complex, but using visual aids such as diagrams, videos [2], or pictures can help students understand the various structures and systems of the body [3].

Then break down the terms: Medical terms often comprise multiple stems, prefixes, and suffixes. Breaking each term into its components and explaining its meanings will help students understand and remember them more easily. Provide real-world examples: Using real-world examples related to medical terminology can help students see how these terms are used in practice and make them easier to understand [2].

Practice, practice, practice: Learning medical terminology requires practice like any new skill. Give students opportunities to use medical terminology in contexts, such as through case studies or patient scenarios. Next, leverage technology: there are many interactive tools and apps that can help students learn medical terminology [4]. These include flashcards, quizzes, and games that make learning fun and engaging. Overall, the key to teaching medical terminology is to make the subject matter engaging and relevant to students' lives and to provide multiple opportunities for practice and reinforcement [5]. In this article, we discuss further in detail those mentioned aspects.

Importance of medical terminology learning. Medical terminology is important because it provides a standardized way for health professionals to communicate with each other about a patient's condition, treatment, and medical history [6]. So, using precise and consistent medical terminology helps avoid misunderstandings and ambiguities that can lead to errors in diagnosis and treatment. For example, "myocardial infarction" is a medical term that describes a heart attack, and using this term ensures that all medical professionals understand exactly what the patient is suffering from [7]. In addition, medical terms can also help patients understand their own health conditions and treatment plans. When medical professionals use medical terms to explain a patient's diagnosis and treatment, it can help patients feel more informed and involved in their own care [7]. Thus, medical terms are an essential component of effective healthcare communication and play a critical role in ensuring the accuracy and safety of patient care.

Sources for Latin medical terms. There are several sources that can be useful for learning Latin medical terms, including. Initially, medical dictionaries: there are

many medical dictionaries that provide definitions and explanations of medical terms, including those with Latin roots. Examples include “Stedman's Medical Dictionary” [9], “Dorland's Illustrated Medical Dictionary” [10], and “Taber's Cyclopedic Medical Dictionary” [11]. Medical Textbooks: Medical textbooks can also be a valuable resource for learning Latin medical terms, as they often contain glossaries or lists of commonly used medical terms. Examples of medical textbooks include “Gray's Anatomy”, “Robbins and Cotran Pathologic Basis of Disease”, and “Harrison's Principles of Internal Medicine” [12]. Online resources: there are many online resources for learning Latin medical terms, including websites, videos, and interactive tools. Examples include the National Library of Medicine's “Medical Subject Headings (MeSH)” database, the “Latin Medical Terms” section of the “MediLexicon” website, and the “Khan Academy's Latin and Greek in Medical Terminology” course [13].

So, medical Professionals: Medical professionals, including physicians, nurses, and medical educators, can be valuable sources of information on Latin medical terms. They can provide context and real-world examples of how these terms are used in practice and advice on how best to learn and retain them.

Central Asian Medical University. I would like to give you with information about my university [14], the Central Asian Medical University in Fergana City. This esteemed educational institution offers comprehensive study programmes in the field of medicine. In close co-operation with universities and medical schools, Central Asian Medical University undertakes the important task of educating and preparing future medical professionals [15].

The academic curriculum at Central Asian Medical University is thorough and challenging, covering a wide range of medical subjects such as anatomy, pharmacology, pathology, microbiology and clinical practise. In addition to the theoretical foundation, our students are required to complete internships in various healthcare facilities such as hospitals and clinics. These practical experiences are important to promote a practical understanding of medical practice [15].

Beyond formal education, Central Asian Medical University is actively engaged in expanding medical knowledge through research initiatives ranging from basic studies to clinical investigations. Our commitment to academic excellence also extends to the provision of continuing education programmes tailored for healthcare professionals. These programmes are designed to keep professionals up to date with the latest developments in the medical field and ensure adherence to best practice [16].

To summarise, the Central Asian Medical University plays a central role in the training of healthcare professionals by combining education, training and research, thus making an important contribution to the advancement of medical knowledge and the improvement of medical practise.

For students: Language learning motives. In the area of foreign language skills, this discourse attempts to make overarching recommendations for language acquisition within the framework of a research article. To begin with, prospective language learners are advised to formulate a clearly defined goal — be it to reach a certain language level or to fulfil a specific purpose such as travelling or professional requirements. The foundation phase is then emphasised, in which learners are encouraged to work on rudimentary elements such as everyday vocabulary, basic grammatical constructions and accentuation in order to build a solid foundation for later learning efforts [17].

A key aspect of language acquisition emphasised in this discourse is the importance of sustained and methodical practise. The recommendation to create and adhere to a systematic schedule, even if it is a modest daily commitment, emphasises the understanding that consistent engagement is central to language mastery. Furthermore, an immersive approach is advocated, encouraging individuals to surround themselves with the target language by approaching it aurally through music, visually through films and series, literarily through books and news articles and, whenever possible, through direct communication with native speakers [18].

A wide range of tools are promoted as a means of improving language skills, including traditional resources such as textbooks alongside modern modalities such

as language learning apps, online courses and participation in language exchange programmes. Patience and perseverance are posited as cardinal virtues, recognising language acquisition as a lengthy endeavour in which setbacks and gradual progress should not deter learners, but rather celebrate the successes along the way [19].

Finally, the discourse appeals to the joy inherent in language learning and encourages learners to bring elements of personal interests and hobbies into the learning process to ensure an enjoyable and fulfilling journey [20]. In summary, this explanation emphasises the nature of language learning as a personal journey of discovery and encourages learners to identify and adopt methods that suit their individual preferences in order to derive maximum satisfaction from the educational process.

Latin Language's Significance. Before we delve into the intricacies of teaching Latin medical terms, it is important to explain the contextual meaning of Latin. Although Latin no longer serves as a spoken language in the traditional sense— - there is no longer an indigenous community — it remains deeply embedded in historical and scientific fields. The historical ubiquity of Latin is evident in various disciplines, especially in medicine, law and science, where a variety of technical and scientific terminologies have their roots in this classical language [21].

Even though Latin is no longer used as a medium of conversation, it is still taught as an academic subject in educational institutions, particularly in the fields of classical literature and history. The relevance of Latin goes beyond the boundaries of individual disciplines. Knowledge of Latin is an advantage in understanding other Romance languages such as French, Italian and Spanish, which trace their linguistic lineage back to Latin [22].

The study of Latin is not only a linguistic but also an intellectual advantage. The analytical demands made by the grammar, vocabulary and syntax of the language promote cognitive skills. Beyond the linguistic and analytical dimensions, Latin contributes to a profound understanding of ancient Roman history and culture and illustrates its lasting influence on Western civilization [23].

To summarise, although Latin has no practical application in everyday communication, its intrinsic value permeates various academic fields. Furthermore, the study of Latin serves as a gateway to multifaceted intellectual enrichment by providing insight into the etymology of scientific jargon, facilitating language acquisition, and fostering an appreciation for the historical fabric woven by ancient Rome. Consequently, the study of Latin becomes a pathway to a broader, more nuanced understanding of various topics, emphasising its continued importance in education today.

Medical terms teaching trends. As someone who knows Latin relatively well, I recognise that my direct insight into current trends in the teaching of medical terminology may be limited. However, it is important to recognise the dynamic nature of medical language, which is constantly evolving due to advances in medical science and technology. With these continuous changes, educators and healthcare professionals must remain vigilant and keep abreast of the latest trends and developments in medical terminology to ensure accurate communication and precise disease diagnosis.

One notable trend in medical terminology education is the increasing reliance on online resources. Interactive applications and virtual learning tools have gained prominence. They provide students with immersive and engaging platforms to improve their understanding of medical language. This shift towards digital resources is in line with the general trend of using technology to optimise the learning experience.

A second notable trend is the adoption of a more visual and interactive approach to teaching. This means using visual aids such as diagrams, videos and animations to explain complex medical terms and concepts. This multi-sensory approach not only accommodates different learning styles, but also facilitates a deeper understanding of complicated medical terminology.

In addition, today's medical terminology training increasingly emphasises cultural competence. Given the diverse patient populations cared for by healthcare professionals, more attention is being paid to incorporating cultural nuances into

medical terminology training. This includes learning the terminology and communication styles specific to different cultural groups to improve patient-physician communication and raise the overall standard of care [24].

In summary, the prevailing trends in medical terminology training emphasise the importance of adapting to the latest developments in medical science and technology. At the same time, instructors are utilising innovative and interactive methods to provide a thorough understanding of medical language. The overarching goal remains to promote effective communication and cultural competence among healthcare providers, improving the quality of patient care in an ever-evolving healthcare landscape [14].

Teaching methodology. The instruction of articles in a foreign language poses challenges, but language teachers can employ various effective methods to enhance comprehension and usage. Firstly, contextualization proves paramount. Furnishing students with real-life situational contexts is essential for a nuanced understanding of how articles function. This involves drawing examples from current events or integrating experiences relevant to the students, fostering a practical grasp of article usage [14].

Authentic materials, such as news articles or magazine features, constitute a valuable resource in elucidating the real-world application of articles. Integrating these materials into the curriculum not only imparts practical insights but also cultivates improved reading and comprehension skills among students.

A foundational aspect of teaching articles lies in explicating the grammatical rules governing their usage. This necessitates a systematic breakdown of article types—definite, indefinite, and zero—accompanied by a comprehensive explanation of the rules governing each category. A thorough understanding of these rules is pivotal for students to navigate the intricacies of article usage.

Consistent practice emerges as a linchpin in honing article usage skills. Through mechanisms such as role-play and written assignments, educators can afford students ample opportunities to apply articles in context. This iterative practice

reinforces comprehension and proficiency, vital components in mastering article usage [14].

Equally crucial is the provision of constructive feedback. Teachers play a pivotal role in guiding students toward improved article usage by correcting errors and elucidating the rationale behind the selection of a particular article in a given context. This iterative feedback loop contributes to a continuous refinement of students' linguistic competencies over time [9].

Thus, effective instruction in article usage within a foreign language necessitates a multifaceted approach. This involves the strategic amalgamation of contextualized examples, comprehensive grammar instruction, ample practice opportunities, and constructive feedback mechanisms. Through these integrated methods, language teachers can empower students to navigate the intricacies of article usage and enhance their linguistic proficiency [8].

The observational method in teaching. In the realm of teaching Latin Medical Terminology, observation emerges as an indispensable instrument, providing valuable insights into students' needs and refining instructional approaches. To enhance the efficacy of this process, I recommend considering the following steps:

Embark on the observation journey by articulating precise goals. Define the specific facets of student behavior, interactions, or learning outcomes that you aim to explore. This clarity in objectives will lend direction and purpose to your observational endeavors.

Select an observation method that harmonizes with the unique dynamics of your medical terminology instruction. Whether opting for direct observation, video recording, or checklists, the chosen method should adeptly capture the nuances intrinsic to the study of Latin medical terms.

Equip yourself meticulously for the observation process. Whether it entails a notebook, camera, or other tools, thorough preparation is paramount. Additionally, secure the requisite permissions from students and parents to ethically conduct observations.

Approach observations with a methodical and consistent framework. Take meticulous notes on targeted behaviors, interactions, and desired learning outcomes. This systematic approach enhances the reliability and relevance of the data gathered, contributing to a more informed assessment.

Engage in a comprehensive analysis of the amassed data from your observation sessions. Seek patterns, identify trends, and recognize outliers. Reflect on what the data reveals about your students and their distinctive needs in grasping Latin medical terminology.

Harness the insights derived from observations to adapt and refine your instructional strategies. This may involve modifying lesson plans, providing additional support or resources, and establishing effective communication channels with students and their parents regarding progress in mastering medical terms.

Cultivate a collaborative milieu by sharing your observations with fellow educators. Collaborate to compare data, discuss findings, and collectively explore ways to enhance instructional strategies. This collaborative ethos contributes to a culture of continuous improvement within the specialized field of Latin Medical Terminology education.

My commitment to the advancement of Latin Medical Terminology education extends beyond the confines of my individual classroom. I actively contribute to the broader educational community by engaging in professional development, sharing best practices, and participating in forums dedicated to enhancing the pedagogy of medical terminology instruction in Latin. This commitment aligns with my overarching goal of fostering a community of educators dedicated to excellence in Latin Medical Terminology instruction.

So, effective observation is integral to empowering educators in the nuanced realm of Latin Medical Terminology instruction. Adhering to the delineated steps—setting clear goals, choosing an appropriate method, meticulous preparation, systematic observation, data analysis, instructional adjustment, and collaborative sharing—affords educators the means to cultivate an adaptive learning environment,

ultimately enhancing student outcomes in the intricate domain of medical language acquisition.

Conclusion. Thus, recommendations for enhancing medical terminology teaching for medical faculty, teachers, and students include employing diverse teaching methods to accommodate various learning styles, integrating real-world examples to contextualize terminology, incorporating interactive activities, utilizing technology, fostering active learning, and promoting a collaborative environment. Effective teaching strategies encompass a multifaceted approach to ensure comprehensive understanding and retention of medical terminology.

Moreover, valuable references for medical terminology include:

Ehrlich, A., & Schroeder, C. L. (Title: "Medical Terminology for Health Professions") - This comprehensive textbook covers anatomy, physiology, medical procedures, and offers interactive learning tools such as flashcards, practice quizzes, and audio pronunciations.

Venes, D. (Title: "Taber's Cyclopedic Medical Dictionary") - A trusted medical dictionary with over 60,000 entries, providing definitions, pronunciation guides, and illustrations for healthcare professionals and students.

Stedman's (Title: "Stedman's Medical Dictionary") - Another comprehensive medical dictionary offering over 107,000 terms, including definitions, pronunciation guides, and illustrations, serving as a valuable resource for healthcare professionals.

Dorland's (Title: "Dorland's Illustrated Medical Dictionary") - An illustrated medical dictionary with over 120,000 terms, featuring definitions, pronunciation guides, and illustrations, along with helpful appendices such as medical abbreviations and symbols.

Fremgen, B. F., & Frucht, S. S. (Title: "Medical Terminology: A Living Language") - Tailored for healthcare students and professionals, this textbook covers medical terminology from a functional perspective, emphasizing practical usage in healthcare settings.

Shokirova M., and Juraev Z. (Title: “Мудрец Латинской Медицинской Терминологии”) - This textbook, written in Russian, is aimed at students and

healthcare professionals, focusing on the functional aspects of medical terminology within healthcare practice.

These resources collectively provide a robust foundation in medical terminology, offering references that can guide and support individuals throughout their careers in healthcare.

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